

Overview and Context

The [second All-Island Cancer Data Forum](#) was hosted by the eHealth-Hub for Cancer at Queen’s University Belfast on 26–27th January 2026, bringing together policymakers, researchers, clinicians, patient advocates and industry from across Ireland, Northern Ireland, and internationally. The Forum gathered an engaged and active community eager to address challenges and identify solutions to enable cancer data-driven patient-centred care, research and clinical decision-making, and develop robust data infrastructure on the island of Ireland and across Europe. Discussions highlighted opportunities to harness data for real-world impact, foster collaborative research networks, influence policy

The Forum took place against a backdrop of a growing cancer burden across the island of Ireland. Cancer remains the leading cause of death on the island of Ireland, accounting for approximately 30% of all deaths annually, with new diagnoses projected to double by 2045 due to population ageing and rising risk factors. This context underscores the urgency of coordinated, data-driven approaches to cancer prevention, care, and research.

This report summarises the proceedings of the 2026 All-Island Cancer Data Forum, highlighting emerging themes and identifying priorities for policy and infrastructure development in cancer data research. It reflects the Forum’s emphasis on practical solutions to fragmented data systems, the primacy of patient-centred research, and the development of sustainable national and all-island capabilities in support of [European Health Data Space \(EHDS\) National Cancer Data Node \(NCDN\)](#) and UK [Health Data Research Service \(HDRS\)](#) readiness.

Key Sessions and Highlights

Recognising the Health and Societal Dividend of Data

Opening presentations highlighted the societal value of cancer data. [Professor Mark Lawler](#) (Queen’s University Belfast, Co-Lead All-Island eHealth Hub for Cancer) emphasised the importance of evidence-driven decision-making. Patient advocate [Margaret Grayson](#) (Northern Ireland Cancer Research Consumer Forum (NICRCF)) illustrated the willingness of patients to permit their data to be used to support research initiatives, and [Professor Aedin Culhane](#) (University of Limerick, Co-Lead All-Island eHealth Hub for Cancer) outlined strategies that the all-island eHealth-Hub for Cancer are undertaking with EU NCDN and UK partners, to convert fragmented data silos into actionable evidence.

Professor Eva Morris, Professor Geoff Hall and Mr Luke Readman in Panel Discussion

Connecting Data: Delivering Real-World Impact

Speakers from the UK and Europe demonstrated how large-scale, interoperable health data can both improve cancer outcomes and save money. [Luke Readman \(NHS England, UK\)](#) described the OneLondon programme; a digital transformation initiative covering a population of 10 million across London, connecting primary GP and ambulatory and hospital data. The eHealthHub for Cancer recently worked with OneLondon to evaluate the programme from a financial and a workforce perspective, estimating financial savings of nearly £18M, coupled with a workforce reduction of 1688 Full Time Equivalents (FTEs). [Professor Eva Morris \(University of Oxford, UK\)](#) highlighted the opportunities and challenges of leveraging big data to understand population level data and drive improvements in cancer care. [Professor Geoff Hall](#) (University of Leeds, UK) discussed how real-world evidence (RWE) research complements randomized clinical trials. Though RWE studies are limited to study of observed routinely collected real world health data which may have data quality or bias issues, these are faster studies to perform and have the major advantage that they include a broader, more diverse patient population in research, including patients who may be excluded from clinical trials due to frailty, co-morbidities, or advanced disease. Panel discussions explored the technical, governance, and policy frameworks required for a connected cancer data ecosystem.

Policy Endorsements and Strategic Direction

The Forum considered the [Harnessing Cancer Data for Better Health](#) seven-point roadmap as a potential framework for future collaboration on cancer data infrastructure. Discussions highlighted the importance of north-south cooperation across genomics, imaging, clinical trial access, data interoperability, patient engagement, and governance. Senior policymakers emphasised the need for strategic investment and aligned governance to maximise the impact of cancer data across jurisdictions.

Dr Stelios Theophanous, Dr Catherine Mahoney, Professor Geoff Hall, Professor Aedin Culhane, Professor Mark Lawler and Professor Dani Prieto-Alhambra

Capability Building: OHDSI Ireland Workshop

OHDSI-Ireland is the all-island Irish “national” node of the global OHDSI (Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics) network, focused on real-world health data and built through the eHealth-Hub for Cancer initiative. [OHDSI-Ireland](#) ran a workshop at the conference, entitled “Foundations in OMOP Common Data Model and Real-World Data: How to Run Your First Real-World Study,” it was the first all-island meeting of the OHDSI Ireland node since its establishment. The workshop was facilitated by Dr Stelios Theophanous (University of Leeds, UK), Professor Geoff Hall (University of Leeds, UK), and Dr Catherine Mahoney (Eli Lilly). It provided practical training on cohort creation, OMOP Common Data Model standards, and federated analysis, enabling real-world evidence studies while

preserving local data control. OMOP is emerging as a key data standards for [secondary data use in the EHDS](#), and also also been adopted as a data standards in HDR-UK, and DARWIN-EU, and is therefore an excellent platform to connect all island health cancer that is being developed for Irish Cancer Data by the eHealth-Hub for Cancer. Feedback was highly positive, demonstrating demand for applied capability development to support EHDS and HDRS readiness.

Realising the Value of Connected Health Data

Presentations on trusted research environments (TREs)/Secure Data Environments (SDEs) highlighted secure data compute and storage platforms for accessing sensitive patient data in Northern Ireland, Scotland, and Europe, emphasising the need to develop standards such that TRE/SDE do not become data silos and can be federated to enable actionable evidence generation. Professor Dani Prieto-Alhambra (University of Oxford, UK) provided an overview of the European IMI EHDEN, the incredible impact of DARWIN-EU, OPTIMA Oncology, and IHI GREG, illustrating how a community of data partners can use OMOP common data model to build federated studies with data from millions of patients to answer critical health problems that accelerate the generation of real-world evidence in cancer research. Dr Christian Cole (University of Dundee, UK) shared lessons from building trusted research infrastructure in the UK, and described the new SATRE guidelines developed in the UK to align TREs across the health sector. The subsequent panel discussion, chaired by Muiris O'Connor (Department of Health, Ireland), explored how these federated approaches can create a sustainable ecosystem for cancer data research, aligning both the EHDS and HDRS across the island.

Professor Mark Lawler, Margaret Grayson, Minister Mike Nesbitt, Miriam Staunton, and Professor Aedin Culhane.

Conroy–Hastings Memorial Session: Delivering for Patients

The Conroy–Hastings Memorial Session brought together a wide range of voices to emphasise that patients and their lived experience must sit at the centre of Ireland's digital cancer future. Chaired by Siobhán Gaynor and Aidan McCormick, the session opened with Miriam Staunton's tribute to Niamh Conroy and James Hastings, two founding UCAN advocates whose legacy of action and partnership continues to shape patient-centred cancer policy, and her announcement of the new Conroy–Hastings Prize. Contributions from Katie Crowley, Caitriona Wray, Amy Nolan, Prof. Micheal Quinn and Prof. Ruth Clifford highlighted the collective challenges and opportunities in building patient-ready digital systems, enabling real-time data use, learning from Northern Ireland's digital transformation, and addressing gaps in areas such as blood cancer data. Across all speakers and discussions, the message was consistent: meaningful patient involvement is essential to designing trustworthy digital health systems, improving outcomes, and ensuring that data serves the people behind it.

Delivering Precision Cancer Medicine

The Forum concluded with sessions on precision oncology, including the integration of genomic and clinical data to create an all-island precision oncology knowledge base. Key contributors included Dr Joep de Ligt (Hartwig Medical Foundation, The Netherlands), Professor Richard Kennedy (Almac Diagnostic Services, Craigavon, UK and QUB), Brendan Reardon (Dana-Farber Cancer Institute / University of Limerick), and Sarah Hersey (Vice President, Precision Medicine, Bristol Myers Squibb/QUB). Discussions highlighted opportunities for EHDS-aligned research to enable personalised care and support real-world evidence generation.

Emerging Themes

1. Infrastructure and Policy Readiness
 - a. The primary constraint is not data availability but aligned governance, infrastructure, and investment.
 - b. EHDS and HDRS provide frameworks for standardised access and federated research.
 - c. Turning data into intelligence is a significant opportunity to drive cancer policy
 - d. Positive feedback from governmental representatives provides an opportunity to advance the cancer data agenda
 - e. The potential for an all island digital powerhouse for cancer data should be explored in more detail
2. Patients as Enablers of Data Use
 - a. Patient advocates demonstrated that transparency, purpose, and clear benefits build trust and facilitate participation.
 - b. Governance measures must balance privacy with research utility to maximise actionable evidence.
3. Capability Building through OHDSI Ireland
 - a. Hands-on training in OMOP and federated analysis bridges the gap between theory and implementation.
 - b. Skills development is critical for EHDS and HDRS readiness.
4. From Memorial to Mechanism
 - a. The Conroy–Hastings Prize embeds patient-centred values into governance and ensures sustained impact.
 - b. Patient-led facilitation of sessions reinforces the centrality of patients in research design and delivery.

Conclusion

The 2026 All-Island Cancer Data Forum provided a vital platform for discussion and debate in relation to cancer data and its health and societal dividend. The Forum demonstrated alignment across policy, research, clinical, and patient communities on the need for multistakeholder partnership, robust infrastructure, capability development, patient-centred governance and deployment of data to drive the policy agenda. By combining actionable strategies, cross-border collaboration, and structured patient involvement, the Forum positioned the all-island cancer data ecosystem to deliver measurable improvements in research, care, and outcomes, while also ensuring EHDS and HDRS-readiness.

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